

Generating (Constraint-) Satisfying Melodies on a Neutral Atom Quantum Computer

Isaiah Hull^{123*}, Moses Hull⁴⁵

¹First QFM
Sweden

²Rethinc Labs UNC
USA

³DeepLearning.AI
USA

⁴Björknässkolan
Sweden

⁵Nacka musikskola
Sweden

Abstract. *Many problems in algorithmic music generation have no known efficient solution on a classical computer. Combining constraints in an arrangement—such as consonance requirements and transition speed limitations—leads to NP-hard problems. We consider the use of neutral atom quantum computers, which have experimentally demonstrated superlinear speed-ups in the solution of certain unit disk maximum independent set (UD-MIS) problems, to solve constrained algorithmic music generation problems. We apply this approach to produce constrained variations of classical guitar melodies.*

1 Introduction

Algorithmic music generation is often geometric in nature [1, 2] and may require the solution of NP-hard subproblems for which no polynomial-time algorithms are known [3]. For example, a musical arrangement that takes a piece written for multiple instruments and attempts to construct an equivalent piece for a single instrument, such as the guitar, will require the imposition of many constraints, such as restrictions on consonance, and limitations on simultaneous notes and transition speeds. Solving for a piece that satisfies all such constraints is an NP-complete problem in many instances [3].

We consider the case of generating melodic variations that satisfy a set of computationally challenging constraints, such as distance from the original piece, pitch choices per note, and maximum interval between notes.

The approach we introduce can be applied either to compose music directly as a sequence of notes and durations or to structure higher-level musical blocks that satisfy musicality constraints. In this sense, the approach can be used to build new styles of music or used in conjunction with tools for music composition, such as generative artificial intelligence (AI) models, which have expanded in use

and quality in recent years [4, 5, 6].

Our work is best characterized as algorithmic composition with rule-based systems, as discussed in Refs. [7, 4]. This literature has increasingly moved towards the formulation of composition problems as constraint satisfaction problems (CSPs) or constraint logic programming problems (CLPs) [4]. Such problems have a worst case time complexity of $\mathcal{O}(d^n)$, where d is the domain and n is the number of variables. In practice, constraints and heuristics are often applied to simplify the problem.

The system we propose in this paper is based around a graphical model of musical elements and constraints. For a survey of the graphical encoding of musical elements, see Ref. [8]. We restrict ourselves to unit disk graphs, where nodes are arranged spatially in a 2-dimensional plane. Edges are indicated by locating nodes within a unit distance of each other.

An edge indicates the presence of incompatible elements in a composition. Solving for the maximum independent set yields a composition that contains the largest sequence of desirable elements that does not violate any of the constraints. There may be multiple maximum independent sets.

The unit disk maximum independent set (UD-MIS) problem is NP-complete. Solving such music generation problems is intractable for large problem instances on classical computing hardware. However, a neutral atom array, which is a specialized quantum computer, may offer scaling advantages for certain UD-MIS problems [9]. As such, quantum computers offer a pathway to the application of more challenging combinations of constraints. We follow a growing literature that uses quantum computation to compose music, including those in Ref. [10].

In addition to introducing methods for music composition using this approach, we also demonstrate how to generate constrained classical guitar melodies using the proposed approach. Specifically, we take a simple classical guitar melody as an input and then generate a variation

*Corresponding author: isaiah@firstqfm.com. Author contributions: Isaiah Hull led the research design, quantum computing methodology, and manuscript preparation. Moses Hull contributed to the musical elements, graphical illustrations, and evaluation of melodic quality. Both authors discussed the results and the final version of the paper.

that is subject to constraints on tone range and distance from the original piece.

The rest of the paper is as follows. In Section 2, we provide the necessary primitives to understand graphical composition, the maximum independent set problem, and the relevant elements of quantum computing. In Section 3, we introduce methods for performing constrained music generation using a graphical encoding. In Section 4, we provide examples of music generated using the proposed system on a quantum computer. And in Section 5, we conclude and discuss the contribution, limitations, and potential future work.

2 Background

Constraint-based music generation systems often attempt to solve problems that have exponential time complexity. This restricts us to the solution of relatively small problems or approximate solutions.

We formulate a set of musical constraints as a UD-MIS problem to facilitate its solution on a neutral atom quantum computer. This offers the possibility of achieving a superlinear speed-up over exact classical solvers [9]. Neutral atom quantum computers have demonstrated value in applications in finance, chemistry, logistics, and mobility [11].

We start by introducing the maximum independent set problem. We then discuss how it can be extended to a weighted maximum independent set problem and how such problems are solved on a neutral atom quantum computer.

2.1 Maximum Independent Set Problem

Throughout this section, we adopt a modified version of the notation in Ref. [12], which provides exact algorithms for solving MIS problems classically.

Let G be a graph, which consists of vertices, V , and edges E . Assume that G is undirected and that $|V|$ denotes the cardinality of the vertex set. Denote the set of vertices as $V(G)$ and the set of edges as $E(G)$.

Let X be an induced subgraph of G with vertex set $V(X) \subseteq V(G)$ and edge set $E(X) \subseteq E(G)$. X is independent if the induced subgraph $G[X]$ has no edges ($E(G[X]) = \emptyset$).

Figure 1 visualizes an independent set. The subfigure on the left shows a randomly-generated Watts-Strogatz graph with a 0.3 rewiring probability. The subfigure on the right illustrates the selection of a subgraph, X , which consists of the red colored vertices, $V(X)$, and the edges that connect them $E(X)$.

The induced subgraph $G[X]$ is an independent set. When we remove the complement of X , no vertices remaining in the graph are connected by edges. That is, $E(G[X]) = \emptyset$.

Let X^* be an independent set. If there does not exist an independent set \tilde{X} , such that $X^* \subset \tilde{X}$ and

Figure 1: Illustration of independent set

$E(G[\tilde{X}]) = \emptyset$, then X^* is a maximal independent set. A maximal independent set is also a maximum if $|X^*| \geq |X|$ for all independent sets $X \subseteq V(G)$.

Finding a maximum independent set for a graph with two vertices is trivial. If the vertices are connected by an edge, either vertex alone is a MIS. Otherwise, both vertices together constitute the unique MIS.

The MIS for the right subfigure in Figure 1 can be identified quickly using an exact solver. However, as we scale the node count, the number of steps needed to find the exact MIS grows exponentially.

Beyond increasing the number of vertices and edges, what distinguishes a hard MIS problem from an easy one? Knowing this will inform sensible decisions about when the use of a quantum computer might be warranted to solve a musical composition problem.

As illustrated in Figure 2, the structure of the graph is another determinant of the difficulty of finding an MIS.

Figure 2: MIS for planar and non-planar graphs

Planar graphs, such the one shown in the left subfigure of Figure 2, are distinguished by the absence of edge crossings. For such graphs, it is possible to find an approximate solution efficiently. Finding an MIS for non-planar graphs with many connections and edge crossings, such as the graph shown in the right subfigure, quickly becomes computationally intractable as the input size scales.

2.1.1 Maximum-Weight Independent Set

A graph may have many maximum independent sets. However, in the context of music generation, we may prefer some of those sets to others based on criterion for musicality, as we will discuss in later sections.

One way to bias the selection of MIS towards more preferable options is to weight the vertices. This is called maximum-weight independent set (MWIS) and is defined below.

For $v_i \in V(G)$, let $w : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be a function that maps vertices to weights, where higher values indicate a stronger preference to include the vertex in the MIS. A set of vertices, X , is an MWIS if $E(G[X]) = \emptyset$ and

$$X^* = \underset{X \subseteq V(G)}{\operatorname{argmax}} \sum_{v \in X} w(v). \quad (1)$$

MWIS maximizes total weight. For the case where weights are equal, MWIS coincides with MIS.

2.2 Neutral Atom Arrays

MIS problems can be solved using several different quantum computing modalities and methods. For example, they can be solved using adiabatic quantum computing or the heuristic version that is practically implementable on D-Wave’s quantum annealers [13]. They can also be solved with the quantum approximate optimization algorithm (QAOA), which can be implemented on gate machines, such as those produced by IBM and Quantinuum [14]. We solve MIS problems on a neutral atom quantum computer, since such devices yield the solution to UD-MIS problems natively by exploiting Rydberg blockades.

There are several producers of neutral atom arrays. We will focus on Aquila, which is a 256-qubit device produced by QuEra. Broadly, neutral atom quantum computers work by arranging individual atoms in a plane using laser tweezers. Atoms may either be in the ground state, $|0\rangle$, or the excited (Rydberg state), $|1\rangle$.

The left panel of Figure 3 illustrates a prospective arrangement of atoms, which serve as vertices in a unit disk graph. Each vertex has a disk drawn around it. When vertices are within a unit distance, as is visually detectable through the intersection of disks, this encodes an edge in the graph, as shown in the right panel.

Figure 3: Unit disk graph and UD-MIS

The red colored vertices in the right panel of Figure 3 form a maximum independent set. Visual inspection indicates that no additional vertices can be added to the set while maintaining the independence property.

Neutral atom quantum computers recover a MIS, such as the one shown, by biasing each individual atom

towards the excited state, $|1\rangle$, which encodes a vertex in an MIS. If atoms were spaced sufficiently far from each other in the plane, all would terminate the process in the excited state; however, when two or more atoms are within a sufficiently short distance of each other, indicated by the disks on the left and the implied edges on the right, only one can be in the excited state. This is a consequence of the ‘‘Rydberg blockade’’ effect.

The Hamiltonian for the Rydberg atom array can be partitioned into a quantum driver, H_q , and a cost function, H_{cost} :

$$H = H_q + H_{\text{cost}}. \quad (2)$$

The quantum driver term is specified as

$$H_q = \sum_i \frac{\Omega(t)}{2} \left[e^{i\phi(t)} |0\rangle_i \langle 1| + e^{-i\phi(t)} |1\rangle_i \langle 0| \right], \quad (3)$$

where Ω is the Rabi frequency, ϕ is the laser phase, and Δ is the detuning.

In most cases, we will assume $\phi = 0$, Ω is constant, and Δ is linearly increasing over the protocol.

The cost function component of the Hamiltonian is specified as

$$H_{\text{cost}} = \sum_i \Delta(t) n_i + \sum_{i < j} V_{ij} n_i n_j, \quad (4)$$

where $n_i = |1\rangle_i \langle 1|$ and $V_{ij} = V_0 / (|r_i - r_j|)^6$. Notice that the first term biases all qubits towards the Rydberg state. The second term captures the ‘‘Rydberg blockade’’: within a certain radius, only one atom will be in the excited state, since it would otherwise have too large an energy cost.

QuEra’s Aquila device solves unit disk MIS (UD-MIS) problem using Rydberg states with the adiabatic state preparation protocol described above. An exact solution to this problem is NP-complete.

Some potential limitations of this approach are the following: 1) existing hardware has 256 qubits, which limits the number of musical elements and constraints that can be encoded in a single problem; and 2) a UD-MIS can be approximated in polynomial time for certain graphs, which suggests that a neutral atom quantum computer might not be needed in those cases if an exact solution is not required.

3 Constrained Melody Generation

Music composition with constraints is a well-explored area of the literature [7, 1, 15, 5]. Using the UD-MIS approach introduced in this paper, we can apply constraints to generate music that satisfies desirable musical properties.

Ref. [4] surveys constraint-based systems for music composition. They find a range of applications, including harmonization, melody generation, polyphonic music generation, improvisation, orchestration, counterpoint, and rhythm.

Constraints can be applied to different compositional elements, ranging from the pitch level to abstract, high-level building blocks.

Within our UD-MIS framework, the distance between nodes is used to encode constraints. For example, if we want to restrict the distance in semitones between two pitches in a sequence, we can place one within the blockade radius of the other in a 2D array.

We might also want to place per-note restrictions on the number of type of pitches. This could be used to reduce dissonance or enforce consistency with a certain type of music, such as fingerstyle guitar.

For concreteness, we illustrate a pitch-level constraint in Figure 4. We assume that pitch A was the previous note and place two restrictions on the following note: 1) only one pitch can be played at a time (no chords); and 2) the interval distance in semitones is restricted.

Figure 4: Unit disk graph and UD-MIS

In Figure 4, the previous pitch (A) is shown in blue. The disk around A intersects with the disks for pitches E and F#, but not for B, C, and D to enforce the restriction on semitone distance. Additionally, the disks for E, F#, B, C, and D all intersect, since they are the prospective next pitches and only one can be selected according to the constraint imposed.

Solving for a maximum independent set with a neutral atom array would yield one of the following options: $\{\{A, B\}, \{A, C\}, \{A, D\}\}$. Any such set would satisfy the constraints imposed.

For such a simple problem, we could use an exact classical solver to recover the set of MIS and sample a valid solution from it. However, for more difficult compositions, we will encounter binding computational constraints on classical computers that may be resolved using

a neutral atom array.

4 Examples of Constrained Variations

We illustrate the method introduced in this paper by producing two examples of beginner-friendly guitar music.

We first take a simple guitar melody and use it to generate a variation that is subject to a set of constraints. This is shown in Figure 5.

In the first step, we take a sequence of pitches and durations from a MIDI file as an input, and perform key detection.

We next apply a pre-processing routine to clamp the melody to the desired MIDI range and to force notes to match the nearest diatonic pitch. This is to enforce that the variation produced matches a simple guitar melody.

The next step is to generate a sequence of candidate pitches. As a parameter of the algorithm, we set the number of candidate pitch options. We also choose the probability of excluding the original pitch from the set of candidates at each step. This increases the distance from the original piece.

Figure 5: Variation generation process

We next construct the conflict graph. For this application, we will impose that only one pitch can be played per note. This can be imposed on a neutral atom quantum computer by stacking all candidate pitches at a time step into a clique.

We also include two conflicts with tunable parameter values: 1) distance from the original pitch; and 2) maximum step size in semitones. In cases where no pitch satisfies all constraints, a fallback choice can be specified, such as the original pitch.

Taking the pitch options and constraints together, we generate a unit disk graph. We then solve the implied

MIS problem, which yields a sequence of pitches. We retain the durations from the original piece.

The example variation we generate is for a simple classical guitar piece: Lightly Row. The original is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Lightly Row

The variation, which is shown in Figure 7, sets the first and last notes to match the original piece, constrains the max step size in semitones to five, and excludes the original pitch from the candidate set at each time step with probability 0.90. Every time step is constructed to admit at least one candidate satisfying the constraints. We solve for the MIS with QuEra’s Aquila device.

Figure 7: Lightly Row Variation

The final composition provides a variation on a beginner-friendly guitar piece that respects all constraints that were encoded in the graph. Melodic leaps are restricted to a narrow range, rhythmic integrity is retained, and the choice of variation distance yields a piece that is clearly identifiable as a variation on the original.

Figure 8 generalizes the illustration in Figure 4 to the full melodic setting for Lightly Row with a stylized example. Candidate pitches form cliques at each time step and conflicts are encoded as edges. MIDI pitches are included as vertex labels. In this example, we add an additional constraint that prohibits the selection of the same pitch twice in a row after the first three introductory notes.

Figure 8: Unit Disk Graph Layout for Intro to Lightly Row

Figure 9 visualizes a conflict graph that illustrates how constraints are embedded for the entire piece. Choices at each time step are indicated by gray nodes. Red edges indicate conflicts across time steps. The blue line indicates an MIS that encodes a variation of Lightly Row that respects the constraints.

Figure 9: Lightly Row Conflict Graph

In the second example, we consider simplifying a classical guitar piece. We follow the same procedure, but impose a different set of constraints: 1) only one pitch can be played simultaneously (no chords); 2) stepwise motion is preferred over large melodic leaps; and 3) multiple repetitions of the same pitch in a sequence should be avoided.

As the original piece, we use Étude No. 1, Op. 1 by Mauro Giuliani. After transposing it into G Major, we map the constraints to a unit disk graph and solve for the MIS.

Figure 10 contains the first two systems of the original piece by Giuliani.

Figure 10: First Two Systems of Étude No. 1, Op. 1

Figure 11 contains the first two systems of the simplified version of Étude No. 1, Op. 1, produced by applying the constraints and solving for an MIS. We use QuEra’s Aquila and partition the piece into two subsequences, solving for the MIS for each and then stitching the components together.

Figure 11: First Two Systems of Étude No. 1, Op. 1 Variation

The resulting variation retains some of the expressive richness of the original while providing a more beginner-friendly piece with pedagogical value.

For both examples, rhythmic correspondences are not directly encoded in the graph. Rather, they are inherited from the original piece or arise through candidate selection. Future extensions might consider explicit rhythm-encoding constraints.

We also restrict constraints to adjacent time steps

for both pieces. The use of Rydberg blockades makes it challenging to link distant notes; however, it is possible using more complex geometric configurations of the time-step cliques. Encoding such relationships is more straightforward with different quantum resources or computing architectures.

The proposed approach can also be applied, in principle, using the maximum-weight independent set problem (MWIS) instead. Here, we could use weighted vertices that bias the MIS towards more desirable musical properties. Recent experimental work suggests that MWIS problems can also be solved on neutral atom quantum computers [14].

5 Conclusion

A large body of work examines algorithmic composition using rule-based systems [7, 4], including more recent work that formulates composition problems as CSPs or CLPs [4].

We propose a rule-based system for algorithmic composition that is structured around organizing constraints into a unit disk graph and then solving for an MIS or MWIS. This yields compositions that contain musical elements that respect the set of constraints imposed. We then show how a neutral atom array can be used to potentially provide a superlinear speed-up in solving certain instances of these problems.

We provide examples of a music generation system that takes a classical guitar melody and constraints as inputs, and yields a variation on the original melody as an output.

Future work could incorporate rhythm-encoding constraints and more complex geometries to capture phrase-level coherence and stylistic features. Weighted formulations (MWIS) offer a way to bias solutions toward stylistic or pedagogical objectives.

References

- [1] Godfried T. Toussaint. Algorithmic, geometric, and combinatorial problems in computational music theory, 2003. Extended version of paper that appeared in: *Proceedings of X Encuentros de Geometria Computacional*, University of Sevilla, Sevilla, Spain, June 16–17, 2003, pp. 101–107.
- [2] Godfried Toussaint. Computational geometric aspects of rhythm, melody, and voice-leading. *Computational Geometry*, 43(1):2–22, 2010. Special Issue on the 14th Annual Fall Workshop.
- [3] William S. Moses and Erik D. Demaine. Computational complexity of arranging music. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1607.04220*, 2016.
- [4] J.D. Fernandez and F. Vico. Ai methods in algorithmic composition: A comprehensive survey. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research*, 48:513–582, November 2013.
- [5] Yueyue Zhu, Jared Baca, Banafsheh Rekabdar, and Reza Rawassizadeh. A survey of ai music generation tools and models, 2023.
- [6] Eduardo Reck Miranda and Hari Shaji. Generative music with partitioned quantum cellular automata. *Applied Sciences*, 13(4), 2023.
- [7] Torsten Anders and Eduardo Reck Miranda. Constraint programming systems for modeling music theories and composition. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 43(4):30:1–30:38, October 2011.
- [8] Joshua Stutter. Data structures for music encoding: tables, trees, and graphs. *Journal of New Music Research*, 0(0):1–14, 2024.
- [9] S. Ebadi, A. Keesling, M. Cain, et al. Quantum optimization of maximum independent set using rydberg atom arrays. *Science*, 376(6598):1209–1215, 2022.
- [10] Eduardo Reck Miranda, editor. *Quantum Computer Music: Foundations, Methods and Advanced Concepts*. Springer Nature Switzerland AG, Cham, Switzerland, 1 edition, 2022.
- [11] Isaiah Hull, Or Sattath, Eleni Diamanti, and Göran Wendin. Introduction. In *Quantum Technology for Economists*, Contributions to Economics, pages 1–9. Springer, January 2024.
- [12] Mingyu Xiao and Hiroshi Nagamochi. Exact algorithms for maximum independent set. *Information and Computation*, 255:126–146, 2017.
- [13] Sheir Yarkoni, Aske Plaat, and Thomas Back. First results solving arbitrarily structured maximum independent set problems using quantum annealing. In *2018 IEEE Congress on Evolutionary Computation (CEC)*, pages 1–6. IEEE Press, 2018.
- [14] Lucas T. Brady and Stuart Hadfield. Iterative quantum algorithms for maximum independent set: A tale of low-depth quantum algorithms, 2023.
- [15] Charlotte Truchet and Gérard Assayag. *Constraint Programming in Music*. ISTE-Wiley, May 2011.